

Emission of CO₂ from spruce soils at the Lyalsky test site (Komi Republic)

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A special role in the carbon cycle belongs to emission of CO₂, which is formed mainly due to the respiration of microorganisms that decompose dead organic matter, and the respiration of plant roots. It should be noted that the ecosystem/soil type, season of the year, and differences between study years have a significant influence on efflux CO₂ from soils. The processes of mineralization and humification in soils occur simultaneously. Therefore, the organic soil matter is both the material for the complete decomposition and emission of CO₂ into the atmosphere, and the source of organic components for the synthesis of humic acids. The aim of the study is to characterize the soil respiration of the middle taiga herb-blueberry and sphagnum spruce forests growing on the Mezensko-Vychegodskaya plains of the Komi Republic.

The work was carried out in the middle taiga subzone of the Komi Republic on the territory of the Lyalsky test site of the Institute of Biology of Komi Science Centre of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences. The study involved herb-blueberry spruce forests on Glossic Stagnic Retisol and sphagnum spruce forests on Histic Stagnic Retisol. Soil respiration measurements were carried out during May–October 2023–2024 using an LI-8100 gas analyzer (LI COR, United States) with a dark soil chamber with a diameter of 20 cm. At the same time, the temperature at a depth of 10 cm and moisture in a layer of 0–5 cm were determined using sensors included with the device. Automatic data loggers HOBO (Onset, United States) were used for continuous hourly recording of soil temperature at the study sites.

In the mid-taiga spruce forests, a “classic” course of the soil respiration curve was observed during the warm period with maximum values in July and August. In a spruce forest on automorphic soil, average monthly values varied in 2023 from 2.6 to 5.4 gCm²/day, in 2024 they varied from 1.3 to 5.1 gCm²/day. Soil respiration of the sphagnum community was 1.2–2.9 times lower ($p_t < 0.05$) in all months except July 2023, when fluxes were comparable ($p_t = 0.126$). Using the soil temperature dynamics at a depth of 10 cm as a predictor, it was calculated that during the warm period, 591–596 gCm² were released into the atmosphere from the surface of the Glossic Stagnic Retisol and 380–421 gCm² from the Histic Stagnic Retisol. The intensity of the C–CO₂ flux during the years of research is comparable with a slightly higher value in 2023. The summer months account for the majority (62–68%) of the warm period C–CO₂ flux. Favorable soil moisture conditions, as well as the presence of a greater number of deciduous species producing easily decomposable litter, caused higher (1.4–1.6 times) losses of C–CO₂ from typical podzolic soil. Soil temperature had a positive effect on emission of CO₂ ($R^2=0.54–0.87$), while soil moisture had a negative effect ($R^2=0.21–0.40$). In the forest on Histic Stagnic Retisol soil, Q₁₀ was higher due to less favorable soil moisture conditions.

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